

Estimation of diosgenin by a direct titration method

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Abstract : A direct titration method of estimation of technical grade diosgenin has been developed by using PSDB reagent. This method is found superior to reported method of estimation by direct titration using the conventional bromine in acetic acid. The new method is more selective in the estimation of the Δ^5 unsaturation of the steroid molecule and relatively free from substitution and oxidation reactions giving reproducible and reliable assay method for screening commercial diosgenin samples.

Keywords : Diosgenin, pyridinium sulphate dibromide.

The steroid industry is based on the use of diosgenin as the starting material for the synthesis of various steroidal drugs. The importance of diosgenin as a raw material in pharmaceutical industry is due to its Δ^5 , 3-hydroxy configuration which permits conversion of diosgenin to 16-DPA and to various steroidal hormones. Since technical and commercial grade diosgenin is a raw material for pharmaceutical industry, it is desirable to standardize a rapid quantitative screening method for batch evaluation of commercial and technical grade diosgenin. Although analytical methods based on gravimetry¹, colorimetry²⁻⁵ and GLC⁶ are reported in literature, the accuracy of these methods are not high since these were developed primarily to ascertain the diosgenin content in dioscorea tubers and, therefore, essentially lack the quality of an assay method for technical samples where higher degree of accuracy is required. Over and above, since trace impurities can highly influence the colorimetric methods, it is mandatory to use cleaning procedures using chromatography prior to colour development. This not only makes the procedure lengthy but also incorporates additional uncertainty in the method of estimation.

Since the Δ^5 unsaturation in the diosgenin molecule is moderately active, a quantitative method for its estimation could be a valuable analytical tool. Nearly all chemical reactions used for determination of unsaturation involve addition of a reagent to the double bond e.g. halogenation, hydrogenation, epoxidation, nitration, thiocyanation etc. Of the various halogenation reactions, the most popular one is the bromination reaction used in various reaction media. Thus, bromine in acetic acid and carbon tetrachloride have been used for the determination of olefinic unsaturation by

early workers⁷⁻⁹. Analytical method based on the addition of bromine to Δ^5 double bond of the diosgenin molecule has been reported in literature^{10,11}. These methods are based on addition of bromine in acetic acid using HgCl_2 or Hg-acetate as catalyst. However, these methods have the inherent disadvantage that apart from the addition reaction which should be quantitative, substitution of organic hydrogen by bromine and also oxidation due to the strong oxidising effect of bromine simultaneously take place. Substitution reaction by bromine lead to erroneous and unpredictable data since it is difficult to control substitution reaction in a large molecule like diosgenin.

One of the more successful reagents for bromination is pyridinium sulfate dibromide (PSDB) originally used by Rosenmund, Kunhenn and co-workers^{12,13}. The active bromine in this reagent does not take part in the secondary reactions of substitution or oxidation. The use of HgCl_2 or Hg-acetate as a catalyst makes the reaction moderately fast for adopting in a classical method for determining olefinic unsaturation. Since diosgenin contained only one unsaturation at Δ^5 position, we thought that selective addition of bromine to this double bond by a reagent slower than bromine in acetic acid could possibly give a quantitative method of estimation in a matrix such as the technical grade diosgenin. The present study aims at finding the correct procedure for selective use of this reagent for diosgenin molecule. The method is applicable to technical and commercial grade diosgenin only. To the best of our knowledge no investigation has been reported highlighting the usefulness of PSDB in the quantitative estimation of technical grade diosgenin.

Results and discussion

Similar to the reaction of olefins which form bromo derivatives by addition of bromine to the double bond, unsaturated steroid molecules also form bromo derivatives, thus offering a reaction for their quantitative estimation. However, unlike the simple olefins, the addition reaction of bromine with steroid molecule is difficult to regulate and substitution reaction also proceed simultaneously due to the complex structure of the steroid molecule offering multiple active centre for substitution. One of the successful methods for bromination is to use 70% reagent in excess in the presence of Hg-acetate catalyst and allowing 30 min for the reaction to complete. We wanted to examine the specificity of this method for the Δ^5 unsaturation in the diosgenin molecule. However, as seen from Table 1, the method based on using excess reagent could not be employed for the estimation of diosgenin. The results were on the higher side for both bromine in acetic acid and also PSDB even under reduced reaction time indicating that excess reagent has an adverse effect and cannot be used as a specific method for the quantitative estimation of diosgenin based on its unsaturation. Also, the data in Table 1 indicated that PSDB was a more specific reagent in the selective addition of bromine to the Δ^5 unsaturation of diosgenin compared to bromine in acetic acid possibly due to its moderate reactivity and less strong tendency for substitution and oxidation reaction.

Table 1. Comparison of rate of bromination of diosgenin in presence of 70% excess reagent

Steroid	Reagent	Mass of steroid/g	Calculated mass of steroid/g			
			Reaction time/min			
			5	10	20	30
Diosgenin (Technical grade, 92% by GC)	1	0.10352	0.10902	0.11220	0.11604	0.12051
Diosgenin (Pure, 98% by GC)	1	0.10165	0.10644	0.10912	0.11294	0.11612
	2	0.10205	0.10435	0.10534	0.10522	0.10681

Reagent 1. Br₂/acetic acid/Hg-acetate.
Reagent 2. PSDB/acetic acid/Hg-acetate.

Table 2 presents the data relating to direct titration of diosgenin by bromine in acetic acid and by PSDB. As seen from the data in Table 2, for technical grade diosgenin and also pure sample of diosgenin, direct titration using bromine in acetic acid indicated percent purity much higher than actual purity of the sample established by other method indicating that the reagent is less specific for Δ^5 unsaturation compared to PSDB. Very good correlations were observed between results obtained by direct titration with PSDB and GLC method indicating the selectivity of the ti-

tration method as adopted by us. Also the standard deviation in the case of bromine in acetic acid was much higher compared to PSDB. It is quite evident, therefore, that PSDB is a more specific reagent for the estimation of diosgenin by direct titration in acetic acid media. The reason for the specific reaction of PSDB with the Δ^5 unsaturation of diosgenin molecule is perhaps due to the slow release of bromine which when present in excess can enter into secondary reactions as in the case of bromine in acetic acid.

Table 2. Determination of diosgenin by direct titration method

Sample	Mass of steroid/g	Estimated Mean		Mass of steroid/g	Estimated Mean	
		purity by Reagent 1	$\pm \delta$		purity by Reagent 2	$\pm \delta$
Diosgenin (Technical grade, 92% by GC)	0.08085	95.7		0.08132	91.8	
	0.08290	94.8	95.86	0.08420	91.9	
	0.08488	96.4	± 1.12	0.08976	91.9	91.94
	0.09055	97.5		0.09445	92.1	± 0.11
	0.10532	94.9		0.10735	92.0	
Diosgenin (Pure, 98% by GC)	0.08136	101.6		0.08088	98.0	
	0.08748	101.6		0.08464	98.1	
	0.08348	101.9		0.08464	98.1	
	0.08520	102.8	102.00	0.08892	98.0	98.02
	0.08896	100.8	± 0.87	0.09262	97.9	± 0.08
	0.10830	102.9		0.10236	98.1	

Reagents 1 and 2 as presented in Table 1.

Experimental

Reagents : Acetic acid, glacial : The acid used was of reagent grade, passing the dichromate test. Bromine in acetic acid : This was prepared with reagent grade bromine using acetic acid as above and the strength was adjusted to about 0.1 N in terms of bromine. Pyridinium sulfate dibromide (PSDB) solution : This solution was prepared as described in the literature¹⁴ and the strength was adjusted to about 0.1 N in available bromine. The solution was stored in an amber bottle in the dark. Potassium iodide, reagent grade : This was used as a 10% (m/v) aqueous solution and was prepared freshly with doubly distilled water. Sodium thiosulphate, 0.05 mol L⁻¹ solution : This solution was prepared and standardized by the accepted method against standard potassium dichromate solution¹⁵. Mercury(II) acetate, 2.5% solution (m/v) : This solution was prepared in glacial acetic acid.

Procedure : Because of the high molecular weight of diosgenin, it was not necessary to prepare a stock solution of the analyte and 0.1 to 0.2 g of technical grade sample was directly weighed in 250 ml iodine flask and dissolved in 20 ml of glacial acetic acid with slight warming to facilitate dissolution. After cooling 10 ml of Hg-acetate solution was added. For procedure using 70% of excess reagent¹⁶ 20 ml of PSDB (or Br₂ in acetic acid) solution was

Note

added and the flask kept in dark for the appropriate reaction period. After the reaction period 150 ml of doubly distilled water was introduced slowly into the reaction flask, followed by 30 ml of 10% potassium iodide solution. Titration with sodium thiosulphate solution was carried out as reported¹⁶, using starch as indicator near the end of the titration. The blank was run simultaneously through whole procedure, omitting only the sample addition and substituting it for 20 ml of glacial acetic acid. The mass of diosgenin was calculated from the bromine equivalent consumed in the reaction.

For direct titration, the sample solution after addition of Hg-acetate was titrated with PSDB (or bromine in acetic acid) using a magnetic stirrer. The reddish brown colour of PSDB (or bromine in acetic acid) solution immediately disappeared and the end point was indicated by the self colour of the reagent stable for 15 s. An automatic dispensing unit (Schött Geräte T-100) was used for controlling the titration. A blank was carried out with the same amount of solvent and catalyst solution omitting only the sample. The percentage of diosgenin was calculated as

$$\frac{(A - B) \times M \times 0.2073 \times 100}{\text{Mass in g of sample}} \quad (1)$$

where A is the sample titre value, B is the blank titre value, M is the molarity of PSDB (or Br in acetic acid).

Conclusion :

We conclude that a titrimetric method for estimation of technical grade diosgenin has been established. We claim

that this method based on PSDB reagent is superior to bromine in acetic acid reported earlier^{10,11}.

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